

Whole-genome sequences of endophytic seed-borne *Bacillus* sp. strains with antifungal properties against *Rhizoctonia solani*

Takwa Marzouk^{1,2*}, Manel Chaouachi¹, Bilel Khiari^{1,3}, Nutan Kaushik⁴, Joe Win⁵, Sophien Kamoun⁵, Naceur Djébali^{1**}

¹ Laboratory of Bioactive Substances, Centre of Biotechnology of Borj Cedria, BP 901, Hammam-lif 2050 Tunisia.

² University of Tunis El Manar, Faculty of Mathematical, Physical and Natural Sciences of 10 Tunis, 2092, Tunis, Tunisia

³ University of Carthage, The National Institute of Applied Sciences and Technology (INSAT) BP 676 Tunis 1080 Tunisia.

⁴ Amity Food and Agriculture Foundation, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida-201313, India

⁵ The Sainsbury Laboratory, University of East Anglia, Norwich Research Park, Norwich, United Kingdom

Corresponding authors: *ingtakwa@gmail.com; [dnaceur2014@gmail.com](mailto:**dnaceur2014@gmail.com)**

Abstract

Here, we report the analysis of complete and annotated genome assemblies of three *Bacillus* sp. strains, two of them belong to *Bacillus subtilis* isolated from organic seeds of tomato and one strain belongs to *Bacillus velezensis* isolated from *Solanum linaenum* seeds exhibiting antifungal activities against the soil borne pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani*. We show that the WGS represents a valuable strategy to highly characterize *Bacillus* strains, and provides greater insight into biocontrol mechanisms which facilitates its applications in the future.

Introduction

Members of the genus *Bacillus* have been used as biocontrol agents to control many soil borne plant pathogens due to their ability to produce antagonistic bioactive substances such as volatile organic compounds (Marzouk et al., 2021) and lipopeptides (Farzand et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021) and to induce systemic resistance (Samaras et al., 2021) in plants. The *B. subtilis* and *B. velezensis* are recognized as safe microorganisms of general interest known to produce a diverse spectrum of secondary metabolites with antimicrobial activity (Liu et al., 2017; Devi et al., 2019; Kiese-walter et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2020). Relatively to *B. subtilis*, *B. velezensis* has been recently described as a potential biocontrol agent (Jiang et al., 2018; Azabou et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020). Except few reports, limited numbers of studies were

interested to prospect the whole genome data of antagonistic bacteria in order to better understand the genetic basis of their biocontrol properties. To do so, the whole genome of selected antagonistic bacteria producing VOCs antifungal activities against *R. solani*, TRC7 and TRC10 strains of *B. subtilis* and SMLR1 strain of *B. velezensis* were sequenced. The *B. subtilis* TRC7 and TRC10 strains produce antifungal VOCs against *R. solani* composed of four major volatiles i.e. Benzenamine, N-ethyl-; 2-Heptanone; Pyrazine, 2,5-dimethyl- and Naphthalene (Marzouk et al., 2021). In addition, the bacterial strains TRC7 and TRC10, and SMLR1 inhibit *R. solani*, *Fusarium solani*, *Fusarium culmorum* and *Fusarium oxysporum* through the production of soluble compounds (unpublished data).

Material and methods

Two *B. subtilis* strains TRC7 and TRC10 isolated from organic seeds of tomato and one *B. velezensis* strain SMLR1 isolated from *Solanum linaennum* seeds were used in this study (Marzouk et al. 2021). For the isolation of endophytic bacteria, seeds of *S. linaennum* and *S. lycopersicum* cv. RioGrande were disinfected using sodium hypochlorite 3 % for 10 min, and washed five times with sterile distilled water and incubated at 25 °C in the dark until appearance of the two first cotyledons. The germinated seedlings were disinfected using sodium hypochlorite 1 % for 3 min, followed by 5 s in ethanol 70 % and then washed five times with sterile distilled water. Disinfected seedlings were aseptically divided into small fragments of cotyledons, stems and roots then placed on Luria-Bertani (LB) medium at 30 °C in dark until appearance of bacterial colonies. Strains were purified on Luria Broth medium at 30 °C and stored in 25 % glycerol at -20 °C.

Whole-genome sequencing of *Bacillus* sp; was performed using Illumina HiSeq, reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic and the quality was assessed using in-house scripts combined with the Samtools, BedTools and bwa-mem software. Then contigs were arranged by using SPAdes software. The assembly features in the table below are calculated using QUAST and The genomes annotation were performed with Prokka. The taxonomic labels identification of the genomes sequences was carried out by Kraken. The DNA extraction, the Illumina genome sequencing and assembly were conducted by MicrobesNG (The BioHub, Birmingham, UK) according to their protocols <https://microbesng.com/>.

Results

Genomic Features

A summary of the genomic features for *B. subtilis* and *B. velezensis* is listed in table 1. Genome assemblies range from 3.9 to 4.2 Mb with up to 72× mean coverage. The number of protein-coding genes for *Bacillus subtilis* (TRC7 and TRC10) was similar (4186 genes); however 3696 genes were predicted for *Bacillus velezensis* SMLR1. The G + C contents of *Bacillus subtilis* (TRC7 and TRC10) and *Bacillus velezensis* (SMLR1) were 43.44 % and 46.46 %, respectively. These assembly statistics show a small difference in G + C content, genome size and amount of protein-encoding genes between the two *Bacillus* species.

Nucleotides sequences accession numbers

The two *B. subtilis* strains TRC7 and TRC10 and the *B. velezensis* strain SMLR1 complete genome sequences have been deposited in the NCBI GenBank under accession numbers are listed in table 1.

Table1: Genomic features of the *Bacillus subtilis* strains TRC7 and TRC10 and the *Bacillus velezensis* strain SMLR1.

Bacterial species	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
Strain	TRC7	TRC10	SMLR1
Genome size (bp)	4180040	4180561	3908767
% GC	43.44	43.44	46.46
Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	10	10	25
Largest contig (bp)	2211281	2211281	795995
Mean coverage (X)	72.3742	129.718	110.643
Number of reads	577965	1119801	902901
N50 (bp)	2211281	2211281	644927
protein-coding gene	4186	4186	3696
tRNA number	85	85	83
tmRNA number	1	1	1
SRA accession numbers	SAMN21908411	SAMN21909380	SAMN21907814

Assemblies accession numbers	JAJCTF000000000	JAJCTG000000000	JAJCTE000000000
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Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being shared prior to formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We encourage and welcome feedback from the community. Please get in touch with ND (dnaceur2014@gmail.com) for more information.

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